

Memorandum of Understanding

The consortia KonsortSWD - NFDI4Society and NFDI4Energy hereby agree to collaborate in the following areas of research data management:

About the consortia

KonsortSWD - NFDI4Society - is the consortium focused on the social, behavioral, educational, and economic sciences. It builds on a network of accredited research data centers (Forschungsdatenzentren (FDZ)) to provide FAIR-compliant (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) access to sensitive data and support researchers across the full data lifecycle.

NFDI4Energy is the consortium for the energy research community, providing services for energy researchers to manage, publish, and reuse data and software throughout the research process. NFDI4Energy sees FAIR data and software as the scientific foundation for a sustainable energy future.

Goals for the collaboration

NFDI4Energy and KonsortSWD jointly target social science in energy research from two perspectives. While KonsortSWD covers the community from a focus of RDM methods, NFDI4Energy has a high focus on the content of the research. To better serve this community, both consortia intend to intensify their collaboration. By combining their expertise, they aim to harmonize their approaches, improve interoperability between service ecosystems and close research gaps in order to create new opportunities supporting this community. This cooperation will thereby simplify future interdisciplinary energy research. Through coordinated efforts, the consortia aim to achieve their common goals more effectively and to foster sustainable progress in research and innovation.

Areas of cooperation

Areas of cooperation include, but are not restricted to:

- Mutual invitations and participation in consortia meetings and conferences
- Creating synergies, e.g., through cooperation of consortia helpdesk, training activities and sensitive data provision
- Joint calls for cross-consortia use cases
- Integration of services into service portfolio
- If data is relevant to both consortia: harmonize data with metadata standards

The consortia plan to **mutually invite** each other to relevant **consortia meetings** and **consortia conferences** (e.g., the yearly NFDI4Energy conference and KSWD).

Thereby, the consortia have opportunities to learn from each other's experiences, exchange insights, and stay updated on the latest developments in the consortia.

Attending each other's events allows members of both communities to meet, network, and foster collaboration and potential joint initiatives. This engagement helps both consortia to align their strategies and to advance their shared objectives more effectively.

The **helpdesks** will **collaborate closely** to allow the communities to access a wider pool of expertise, receive faster and more accurate support, and benefit from shared resources and best practices. This enhances user support and improves efficiency. Likewise both consortia plan to collaborate in the area of **trainings** by identifying areas for harmonized training material, expertise and best practices. They foster networking and collaboration among members, while increasing efficiency through shared resources and coordinated efforts. NFDI4Energy agrees to follow the training courses offered by KonsortSWD. Joint training materials for social scientists in energy research will be developed by NFDI4Energy for the use in both consortia. KonsortSWD will help adopt best practices for sharing privately held data to the energy sector. Should interest arise in providing sensitive, privately held data in the energy data, KonsortSWD will be happy to provide its expertise.

The consortia plan to issue **cross-consortia use case calls**. A use case demonstrates RDM services, concepts and processes in realistic projects with a typical research question to establish these and support their use in the community. By providing example applications, tutorials or best practices or making existing data easily accessible, a use case aims to improve RDM processes throughout the research lifecycle. It becomes cross-consortial if it uses services from both consortia and makes a service from one consortia usable for the other. This allows them to combine their expertise, share insights and develop practical solutions to common problems.

NFDI4Energy and KonsortSWD plan to collaborate to **enable a research data center (RDC)** for social energy research. This RDC should be **accredited by RatSWD** and should be part of the **service portfolio of NFDI4Energy**.

Signatories of the memorandum

For KonsortSWD

- Christof Wolf (GESIS)

For NFDI4Energy:

- Astrid Nieße (Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg)

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